

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B050
 Date: 06 Sep 2004
 Take Off: 07:58:03
 Landing: 12:51:52
 Flight Time: 4h53m49

Trials Instructions: ADRIEX – flight over Northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley
Operating Area: N Adriatic and Po Valley, Italy

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Simon Osborne	Reading University
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
9	VACC	Stuart Heath	FAAM
10	Cloud Physics (2-D)	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
11	SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
12	Filters	Paola Formenti	CNRS/University of Paris 12
13	AMS	Jonny Crosier	UMIST
14	TDL / WAS / PAN / Tubes	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
15	Nephelometer / PSAP	Jolene Cook	Reading University
16	Mission Scientist 2	Ellie Highwood	Met Office
17	Mission Scientist 3	Elisabeth Ostrom	Met Office
18	Observer	Nick Price	FAAM
19	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
20			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B050
 Date: 6th September 2004
 Project: ADRIEX
 Location: Po Valley

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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064330		UBBRs	-.25 kft	027	Covers OFF @0610
070702		test	-.26 kft	027	
073747		INU	-.26 kft	027	To NAVIGATE
075803		T/O	1.0 kft	245	Treviso
080239		Videos	4.7 kft	128	Start recording
081144	081347	Profile 1	4.7 - 3.0 kft	296	1000fpm
081508	082024	Profile 1	3.0 - 0.05kft	158	500fpm
082024	082520	Profile 2	0.05- 3.0 kft	162	500fpm
082524	083137	Profile 2	3.0 - 10.0 kft	159	1000fpm
083342	083553	Profile 2	10.0 - 12.4 kft	346	1000fpm
083735	084020	Profile 2	12.4 - 15.0 kft	351	
084736		Sonde	15.0 kft	349	Launch 01, on RFC
084742		Sonde	15.0 kft	349	
084941	085324	Profile 3	15.0 - 12.0 kft	175	
085415		Sonde 01	12.0 kft	177	Splashdown
085420		Sonde 02	12.0 kft	177	Splashdown
085734	090335	Run 1	12.0 kft	136	Into Sun
090522	091049	Profile 4	12.0 - 6.6 kft	309	1000fpm
091433	092435	Run 2	6.5 kft	142	Into Sun
092435	092903	Profile 5	5.6 - 3.0 kft	141	
093106	094108	Run 3	3.0 kft	326	Down Sun
094243	094656	Profile 6	3.0 - 0.73 kft	127	1000ft
094829	095029	Profile 6	0.72 - -.17 kft	334	1000 - 100ft
095030	100034	Run 4	-.17 - -.16 kft	330	Down Sun, 100ft
100549	100723	Orbit 1	0.21 - 0.20 kft	064	40deg, RH,start 060
100806	100937	Orbit 2	0.20 - 0.22 kft	135	Start 150deg, 500ft
101026	101156	Orbit 3	0.18 - 0.19 kft	237	Start 240, 500ft
101248	101418	Orbit 4	0.22 kft	322	Start 330
101944	102117	Orbit 5	0.19 - 0.20 kft	306	start 330
102214	102348	Orbit 6	0.23 kft	059	Start 060
102432	102603	Orbit 7	0.26 - 0.23 kft	131	Start 150
102652	102824	Orbit 8	0.22 - 0.27 kft	234	220
102943	103133	Profile 7	0.38 - 1.7 kft	104	Int @ 2kft
103250	103421	Profile 7	1.7 - 2.6 kft	330	500fpm
103500	104920	Run 5	2.7 kft	199	A to B
105209	110911	Run 6	2.7 kft	326	B to C
111041	112236	Run 7	2.7 kft	205	C to D
111111		Videos	2.7 kft	204	Change Tapes
112344	113628	Run 8	2.7 kft	339	D to E
113902	114906	Profile 8	2.7 - 15.0 kft	146	E to D, 1000fpm
113954		PSAP	3.5 kft	147	Pump OFF
114119		PSAP	4.9 kft	145	New Filter, Pump ON
115137	120208	Profile 9	15.0 - 2.7 kft	044	D to C, 1000fpm
120455	122031	Run 9	2.7 kft	151	C to B
122155	123234	Run 10	2.7 kft	032	B to A
123234	123507	Profile 10	2.7 - 4.7 kft	029	End at Alpha
123817		PSAP	4.8 kft	222	Pump OFF
125152		Land	-.23 kft	069	Treviso
125452		GPS Posn	-.23 kft	023	45'39.16N, 12'12.06E

B050 Track 06-SEP-04

FAAM Sortie Brief

Flight number: B050

Date: 6th September 2004

Purpose: ADRIEX flight over Northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley

Weather: Anticyclonic curvature; predominantly cloud free; heavy pollution preferred.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off Treviso 08:00Z
2. Transit to Point A at low level but including period at 5000ft (10mins)
3. Interrupted profile ascent from 50' to FL150 over point A. (Ocean Tower: 45°18'50''N, 12°30'28''E) (30mins)
4. Dropsonde #1 at FL150
5. Stacked profile descent with ~4 SLRs of 10 minute duration oriented into and down sun at various levels to be determined by the aircraft scientist over point A (90 mins)
6. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~40deg) at 500ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (100mins)
7. Holding pattern for 10 minutes (110mins)
8. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle (~40deg) at 500ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (120mins)
9. Interrupted profile ascent from 500ft to 3000ft over point A (130mins)
10. SLR at 3000ft from A to point B (44°30'N, 12°00'E) (145 mins)
11. SLR at 3000ft from B to point C at Soave (45°25'N, 11°15'E) (160 mins)
12. SLR at 3000ft from C to point D at Reggio Nell Emilia (44°42'N, 10°32'E) (175 mins)
13. SLR at 3000ft from D to point E at (45°30'N, 10°00'E) (190 mins)
14. Profile ascent to FL150 from E to point D (205mins)
15. Profile descent to FL150 to 3000ft from D to point C (220mins)
16. SLR at 3000ft from C to point B (235mins)
17. SLR at 3000ft from B to point A (250mins)
18. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle+10deg at ~1000ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (260mins)
19. Holding pattern for 10 minutes (270mins)
20. Set of banked orbits over point A at the solar zenith angle+10deg at ~1000ft or above any marine boundary layer pollution as advised by the aircraft scientist. (280mins)
21. Interrupted profile ascent from 50ft to FL150 over point A (295mins)
22. Dropsonde #2 at FL150
23. Recover to Treviso.

Point A Ocean Tower	45°18'50''N, 12°30'28''E
Point B	44°30'N, 12°00'E
Point C (Soave)	45°25'N, 11°15'E
Point D (Reggio Nell Emilia)	44°42'N, 10°32'E
Point E	45°30'N, 10°00'E

Aircraft Scientist debrief sheet

B050

6th September 2004

Weather conditions:

High pressure centres over the UK and far eastern Europe bringing slack northeasterly winds at the surface over the Adriatic. Mostly stable over the region, significant non-precipitating cloud over land surrounding the Adriatic, but largely clear over the northern Adriatic.

Aims of the flight:

To carry out radiometric and in-situ measurements of pollution aerosols originating in the Po valley, both over land in order to sample the microphysics and chemistry near the aerosol sources, and within aerosol that has been advected out over the northern Adriatic.

Summary of the flight:

A very successful sortie brings to a close a very successful detachment. Conditions over the sea were good for radiation work i.e. cloud free. A profile from 50' to FL150 was carried out over point A (ocean tower). A surface mixed layer was evident up to ~600' which was polluted; the main pollution layer was obvious up to ~FL090 where a strong inversion created a sharp cap to the pollution plume. Cu clouds over coastal regions could be seen just bubbling through the inversion. 2 dropsondes were released at FL150. Some elevated aerosol was sampled at the altitude that was distinctly different, albeit light in loading, from the Po valley pollution below. CN counts were ~900/cc with the CO also registering significant mixing ratios. Maybe aged biomass burning aerosol ? Straight and level runs were carried out during a profile descent at the following levels:

- (i) FL120, into Sun, above main pollution
- (ii) FL065, mid pollution layer, into Sun
- (iii) 3000', in pollution, down Sun
- (iv) 100', in SML, still polluted; significant loadings of CN compare to above

The wind at the surface was a bit higher than on previous flight, 15-20 kts. Sea state was 5. Two sets of 4 orbits, banked at 40deg right wing down, were then performed at an altitude of 500'. The SWS filters were removed between the two sets. The aerosol loadings within the main pollution layer were similar to previous sorties, but the distribution in the vertical was different i.e. it was relatively well mixed from ~1000' up to FL090.

After a re-positioning profile was carried out up to 3000' towards point A, a raster pattern was flown at this height over land, with turns at points B, C, D and E. Aerosol concs were variable during these runs: PCASP 500-1000/cc, CN 20,000-80,000/cc, CO variable but typically 140ppbv. Concs on the whole were higher than over the sea. Some distinct

plumes were flown through, in particular around point C. Cloud cover varied from 1-2/8 cu nearer the coast to 8/8 Sc around point E; cu bases were around 4000ft. The Sc was a little higher than this. A profile climb through the Sc layer was carried out from E to D, followed by a descent from D to C. 3000' straight and level runs brought us back to B and then A. A short profile climb to 5000' over point A completed to sortie.

The PCASP heaters were switched off until the start of run 9 (point C returning back to point A), when they were switched on for the remainder of the flight.

Instrument faults:

PCASP bins 1-3 u/s.

CVI PCASP bin 1 u/s.

Aerosol mass spectrometer: fell over early in the flight, but was brought back to life which justified carrying out the Po valley runs which was partially planned for the AMS.

No other significant problems.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S. R. OSBORNE

Flight No **B.050**
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Date 06/09/04

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0758					T/O TRIVISO AIRPORT 1/8 cloud cover. and airf... Fairly wazy conditions.
0809		5000'	125	45.2 12.6	v. white haze over sea poor VIS passed under some Ci and was like, but seems clear at this time.
081145	P1 ↓	5000' ↓	295	45.2 12.7	Start profile ascent in ascent. hdg towards coast. Can see cloud over the land.
081354	P1 →	3000'		45.3 12.5	Enterpt, profile to head left. PMSR hts off.
081506	P1 ↓	3000' ↓	158	45.2 12.4	Re-start profile descent Sea state ^{maybe} ~ 5. ~ 19 kts? mod.
081910		1400'			winds ^{m/s} 03 / 42°
		500'			top of SML? winds 9 m/s. / 32°
082026	P1	50'	102	45.9 12.6	End profile descent to 50' / Start P2 descent
	P2 →	600'			CO ~ 145 ppbv.
	P2 →	1850'			poor VIS. white horizon
082509		3000'			1000 ft / mi. Peak = ascent?
		3800'			Temp. increasing 220/PC
		5000'			clear of cloud all around.
		2500'			Ascent about 500 ft descent
					Go to our right. slides
					Emersion (quite strong) ↳ building New Investigation.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

}
}
 FL120
 6500'
 3000'
 100'
 }
 4 levels.

Flight No **B**.....050.....
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
083140	P2	FL100	159	44.3 12.9	Interrupt profile ascent.
083345	P2A	FL100			Re-start profile ascent.
		FL100			aerosol counts low now.
083556	P2	FL124		44.4 12.7	Interrupt profile ascent.
		FL135			con to p2b.
083734	P2A	FL125	351	44.5 12.7	Re-start profile ascent in clear air.
					clear skies above.
084012	P2	FL150	352	44.7 12.6	End profile ascent above all aerosols.
084735	-	FL150		45.3 12.5	DROPSONDE #1 !! CN counts
084740	-	FL150		45.3 12.5	DROPSONDE #2 !! ~ good
084941	P3J	FL150	177	45.3 12.6	Start profile descent: ^{tops} _{and winter mixing.} Good 1 layer to pollution layer below.
085323	P3	FL130	177	45.0 12.5	End profile descent.
085737	B1	FL130	139	44.7 12.6	Start SLR into Sun above ^{top.} _{air.} EPL. [Tr. med. cloud/ aerosols]
090025	P4	FL120			Tr. CN to out flight. Crystal clear above. CN ~ 500/cc ^{Lowest clear flux} _{≈ 85 h/m²}
090337	P1	FL120	136	44.4 12.7	End SLR above pollution layer.
090523	P4J	FL120	310	44.4 12.9	Start profile descent into pollution.
	P4J	FL100			Skies above EPL.
		9500'			Inversion + aerosol increase, slightly turbulent.
091049	P4J	6500'	351	44.6 12.5	End profile descent in EPL (mid way)
		6500'			CN 2000/cc

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....050.....
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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
094435	P2	6500'	142	44.7 12.4	Start SCR. in mid ORL. Good ineq signal. ^ 4000 / 4 on P2ASP P2AP ~ $4.4 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ D2P ~ $2.5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ w_0 uncorrect ~ 0.85
094435	P2	6500'	142	44.2 11.9	End SCR
094446	P5	6500' 3500'			Start profile descent within pollution. Neph. sig. fairly low. with height.
094902	P5	3000'	143	44.0 13.1	End profile descent in pollution.
094903	P2	7000'	326	44.0 12.2	Start SCR * DOWN SUR * Neph slightly "inside" here. P2AP = $2.8 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ with lower here.
094946					Neph / P2AP high in - Doubled! plume structure? Rise in SO also
094920	P6	3000' ↓	127	44.5 12.8	Start profile descent in base of pollution
094954	A	2000'		44.4 13.0	Restart profile descent.
094930	P6	1000'	333	44.4 13.1	Restart profile descent.
0950	P6	1000'	330	44.5 13.0	End profile descent. / Start SCR SS(4-5) Now filter
100034	P4	100'	334	45.0 12.6	End SCR in 5mC, transit to point A
100547	01	500' ORL		45.3 12.5	Start orbits. 41° right wing down clear skies all around.
100721	012	500'			End orbit extend out. Diverging
100804	02	500'			

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
100936	02	500'		45.2 12.6	End orbit.
101023	03	500'			Start orbit.
101155	03	500'			End orbit.
101246	04	500'		45.2 12.5	Start orbit. (1st last of 1 st set)
101417	04	500'			End orbit.
					Holding pattern for 5WS.
101942	05	500'		45.2 12.5	Start next orbit ^{set of} (sus ritter unit)
102116	05	500'			End orbit. 40" right wing down.
102215	06	500'			Start orbit
102327	06	500'		45.2 12.4	End orbit.
102430	07	500'			Start next orbit.
102601	07	500'		45.2 12.5	End orbit.
102651	08	500'			Start last orbit of 2 nd set.
102827	08	500'		45.2 12.5	End last orbit of 2 nd set.
102943	P2	600' P1	105	45.2 12.5	Start profile climb. to 3000'
103132	P2	200'	102	45.2 12.6	Interrupt profile ascent.
103249	P2	200'	329	45.2 12.6	Re-start profile ascent. towards point A
		220'			Map. signal rising.
103419	P2	3000'	320	45.3 12.5	End profile ascent around point A.
1035	R5	3000'	200		Start run A → B ^{slow} _{slow}
					counts rising. Press ~ 600/cc
					CN ~ 20,000/cc.
					(CUI = 1000/cc. (bin out))
					CPC3016 = 8500/cc.
					(a survey 500-1000' above us)

(Ground conditions.
Can handle the Cu)

↳ top of CBL?

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date **06/09/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104920	R5	3000'			End point at BRAVO.
					cn very variable.
105208	R6	3000'	326	44.5 12.0	SLR B → C good level! (uncorr. CO ₂ 20.85)
					(O ₃ = 56 ppb CO = 136 ppb NO _x = 0.09 ppb NO ₂ = 1.05 ppb SO ₂ = 2.2 ppbv.)
1106	R6				Some Ci above. No cloud above but +CN + neph. PMS? ins? localised plume?
1109					
110910	R6	3000'	333	45.3 11.2	End run @ point C.
111035	R7	3000'	205	45.3 11.1	Start SLR C → D
111200	R7	3000'			Some Ci above now, as well as 28 cu
1113	R7				hodos water ahead.
1115					CN ~ 75,000/cc !!
					Quite a bit of structure along R7
					[MRFO24] Better than over stable turning
112242	R7	3000'	2	46.6 10.5	End Run @ D inside turn.
112343	R8	3000'	341	46.7 10.4	End Run D → E.
1124	R8	3000'			Neph dropped in signal → over vis decreasing towards E.
1127					6/8 cloud above. Curt sheet
1129					8/8 cloud cover now. cloud above sheet
1132					PSAP = $11 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$ OSP = $45 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$

Some over points

28 cu

R7

over turning way

cloud above sheet

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date **06/07/04**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1134	R8	3000'			Clouds dropping off now ^{eg. Napf/CNC}
113626	R9	3000'	337	45.4 10.0	End Run at point E.
113701	P8	3000'	148	45.3 10.0	Start profile ascent to P150. End Hit cloud → high Sc.
	P8	P150			End profile ascent at point D
	P9	F150			Start profile descent to point C T/S on P9 longer than on P8.
115853					Hit cloud (Cu) briefly.
120455	R9	3000'	152	45.3 11.2	Start run @ point C SLR in pollution.
1209	R9	3000'			cloud has now descended to 1/8 Cu No Ci above that
1211					RCASP ~ 5500cc but variable.
121332	P9	3000'			Over Po river now. Poor vis along this run. Ca 14ppm O ₂ 62 NO 208 NO ₂ 1.6 ^{ppb} SO ₂ 3.80 ppb.
122032	R9	3000'		44.5 11.9	End SLR @ point B.
122158	R10	3000'	031	44.5 12.0	Start SLR B → A (chemistry cal for 1 st 2 miles of run)
1227					RH ~ 91%
1231					Over sea now.
123219	R10	3000'	030	45.1 12.5	End SLR 10 miles from point A.
123230	P10	3000'	-		Start profile climb to 5000' Napf vis in climb.
123506	P10	5000'	011	45.2 12.4	End profile ascent at point A

End of science.

RCASP
HTRS
ON
FOR
REST
OF
SCIENCE

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B050

Date: 6/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:11:48	600		0	2							Start Profile 1 from 5000'
08:12:40	515			2							4000'
08:13:50	410			2							3000'
08:16:35	400			5							2000'
08:18:40	400			5							1000'
08:19:39	500			5							500'
08:20:24	600			5							End of P1 Start Profile 2 @ 500'
08:22:57	400			5							FL010
08:24:21	350			5							FL020
08:25:30	300			5							FL030
08:26:25	220			5							FL040
08:27:22	220			5							FL050
08:28:04	190			5							FL060
08:28:52	170			5							FL070
08:29:45	150			2							FL080
08:30:40	130			2							FL090
08:31:36	4			1							FL100
08:34:37	3										FL110
08:35:30	2										FL120
08:38:23	0										FL130
08:39:30	5										FL140
08:40:20	5										End of Profile 2 @ FL150
08:49:41	10										Start Profile 3 from FL150
08:51:21	20										FL140
08:52:22	10										FL130
08:53:26	10										End of Profile 3 @ FL120
08:57:39											Start Run 1 @ FL120
08:58:00	5										
09:00:00	5										
08:02:00	3										
08:03:36											End of Run 1
08:05:26											Start Profile 4 from FL120

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:07:38	60		0								FL100
09:08:36	180										FL090
09:09:28	280			2							FL080
09:10:18	340			2							FL070
09:10:53	400			2							End of Profile 4 @ FL065
09:14:38											Start Run 2 @ FL065
09:15:00	315			2							
09:17:00	320			2							
09:19:00	310			2							
09:21:00	280			2							
09:23:00	300			2							
09:24:06											End of Run 2
09:24:48											Start Profile 5 from FL065
09:25:35	345			2							FL060
09:26:46	400			2							FL050
09:27:44	440			2							FL040
09:29:10											End of Profile @ 3000'
09:31:09											Start Run 3 @ 3000'
09:32:00	340			2							
09:34:00	350			2							
09:36:00	320			5							
09:38:00	380			5							
09:40:00	550			5							
09:41:11											End of Run 3
09:42:46	600			5							Start Profile 6 from 3000'
09:44:30	660			5							2000'
09:46:55	720			5							1000'
09:50:25	600			10							End of P6 Start Run 4 @ 100'
09:51:00	570			10							
09:53:00	450			10							
09:55:00	440			10							
09:57:00	440			10							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

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Date: 6/9/04

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:59:00	380		Overheat	10							
10:00:39											End of Run 4
10:14:22											Start Orbits
10:19:46											End of Orbits
10:19:48											Start Orbits
10:28:58											End of Orbits
10:29:43											Start Profile 7 from 100'
10:30:33	340			5							FL010
10:33:21	400			5							FL020
10:34:21	500			5							End of Profile 7 @ 3000'
10:35:00											Start Run 5 @ 3000'
10:42:00	600		On	5							
10:44:00	470		0	5							
10:46:00	455			10							
10:48:00	460			5							
10:49:20											End of Run 5
10:52:13											Start Run 6 @ 3000'
10:53:00	430			5							
10:55:00	470			5							
10:57:00	460			5							
10:59:00	440			5							
11:01:00	460			10							
11:03:00	440			5							
11:05:00	350			5							
11:07:00	420			5							
11:09:00	440										
11:09:12											End of Run 6
11:10:38											Start Run 7 @ 3000'
11:11:00	500			5							
11:13:00	600			5							
11:15:00	370			5							
11:17:00	470			5							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B050

Date: 6/9/04

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:19:00	470		1	10							
11:21:00	600			5							
11:22:41											End of Run 7
11:23:45											Start Run 8 @ 3000'
11:24:00	810			10							
11:26:00	800			10							
11:28:00	780			10							
11:30:00	680			10							
11:32:00	590			5							
11:34:00	510			10							
11:36:00	600			10							
11:36:30											End of Run 8
11:39:00											Start Profile 8 from 3000'
11:40:27	310			15							FL040
11:41:28	260			5							FL050
11:42:15	380			5							FL060
11:43:08	500		17	1000							FL070
11:43:40	560		55	1000							FL080
11:44:26	5		73								FL090
11:45:10	10		73								FL100
11:45:54	10										FL110
11:46:45	10										FL120
11:47:37	5										FL130
11:48:35	5										FL140
11:49:10	2										End of Profile 8 @ FL150
11:51:42	3										Start Profile 9 from FL150
11:52:49	4										FL140
11:55:05	500			5							FL070
11:59:10	700			5							FL060
12:00:15	800			5							FL050
12:02:10	700			5							FL040
12:02:13	550			5							End of Profile @ 3000'

SWS/SHIMS PRE-FLIGHT LOG		Date	6/9/04	Flight	B 01A 050
Operator(s)	A. Wilson		Campaign	ADRIEX	
Departure	06		Arrival	06	

Physical system setup

Module Number <i>Serial</i>	Connection(e.g.SWS nir, SHIMS upper)
0	SWS NIR
27581	SWS VIS

System functionality check **After system stabilizes**

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0 sec	at time	063000 Z
Freezer temp				

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 058	Date	6/9/04	Operator(s)	A. Wilson	log page	1	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

*
Filters
in
ND3.0
Both VIS
&
NIR
|

073500						Filters fitted pre-flight ND3.0 in VIS & NIR			
074300						DARK CURRENT			
075800						VIDEO START			
075815						take off.			
080022						DATA start.			
081144	P1	500ft	180°	Auto		Start P1 → 50ft			
081347	P1	300ft	180°	Auto		int P1			
081508	P1	300ft	180°	Auto		Restart P1			
082024	P1	50ft	180°	Auto		end P1 @ 50ft			
	P2	50ft	180°	Auto		start P2 → PL150			
082520	P2	300ft	180°	Auto		int P2			
083342	P2	300ft	180°	Auto		Restart P2			
083553	P2	124	180°	Auto		int P2			
083735	P2	124	180°	Auto		Restart P2 → 150			
084020	P2	150	0°	Auto		End P2 @ PL150			
084941	P3	150	0°	Auto		start P3 → PL120			
085324	P3	120	0°	Auto		end P3 @ PL120			
085742	R1	120	54°A	Auto		PL120 Sun run @ PL120 - 1 sec sample zenith 47.5 pitch 6°			
0903	R1	120	54°A	Auto		end R1 - Good run - solar position held well, run above polluter.			
090522	P4	120	40°A	Auto		start P4 → PL065			
091049	P4	065	40°A	Auto					
0911433	R2	065	52°F	Auto		start R2 - into sun @ PL065 zenith 45.8 pitch 6.1.			
092435									
092435	R2	065	49.52°F			end R2			
092435	P5	065	48°F	Auto		Start P5 → 300ft			
092903	P5	300ft	48°F	Auto		end P5 @ 300ft			
093106	R3	300ft	37°A	Auto		start R3 @ 300ft. Down Sun. Az, zenith 43.2 pitch 6.2°			
						Down sun measurements are greatest using INS heading 101.8° over solar azimuth.			*
094108	R3	300ft	36°A	Auto					
094243	P6	300ft	0°	Auto		start P6 → 100ft			
094725	P6	100ft	0°	Auto		int P6			
095027	P6	100ft	0°	Auto		restart P6 → 100ft			
	R4	100ft	34°A	Auto		start R4 @ 100ft			↙ down sun run
	P6					end P6 @ 100ft			↘
1000	R4	100ft	34°A	Auto		end R4.			

094830

NEXT page.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B050** Date **6/9/04** Operator(s) **A. Wilson** log page **2** of **3**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

100335	orbit 1		6°F	10	30	in prep. for orbits. Sample period 0.2sec
100549	orbit 1	500ft	6°F	10	30	start orbit 1. 40° right wing down
100723	" 1	500ft	6°F	10	30	end 1
100806	" 2	500ft	6°F	30	50	start 2 - @
100937	" 2	500ft	6°F	30	50	end 2 - Good signal.
101026	" 3	500ft	6°F	30	50	start 3 - start 3
101056	" 3	500ft	6°F	30	50	end 3 - Great signal again
101248	" 4	500ft	6°F	30	50	start 4 - start 4
101418	" 4	500ft	6°F	30	50	end 4 - Great signal.
						Filters removed
101944	orbit 5	500ft	6°F	10	10	start 5. Sample period 0.1 sec.
102117	" 5	500ft	6°F	10	10	end 5. good data
102214	" 6	500ft	6°F	10	10	start 6
102348	" 6	500ft	6°F	10	10	end 6 good data
102432	" 7	500ft	6°F	10	10	start 7
102603	" 7	500ft	6°F	10	10	end 7 good data
102652	" 8	500ft	6°F	10	10	start 8
102824	" 8	500ft	6°F	10	10	end 8 - all good orbits
102943	P7	500ft	0°	Auto		start P7 → 300ft. Sample period 1 sec
103133	P7	200ft	0°	Auto		int P7
103250	P7	200ft	0°	Auto		restart P7 → 300ft.
103421	P7	300ft	0°	Auto		end P7 @ 300ft
103500	R5	300ft	0°	Auto		start R5 → A → B
104920	R5	300ft	0°	Auto		end R5 @ B
105209	R6	300ft	180°	Auto		start R6 B → C
100911	R6	300ft	180°	Auto		end R6 @ C
101041	R7	300ft	0°	Auto		start R7 C → D
112236	R7	300ft	0°	Auto		end R7 @ D
112344	R8	300ft	180°	Auto		start R8 D → E
113628	R8	300ft	180°	Auto		end R8 @ E
113902	P8	300ft	0°	Auto		start P8 → PL150
115137	P8	150	0°	Auto		end P8 @ PL150
	P9	150	0°	Auto		start P9
120242	P9	300ft	0°	Auto		end P9
120455	R9	300ft	180	Auto		start R9 C → B
120741						Video Start.
122031	R9	300ft	180°	Auto		end R9 @ B
122155	R10	300ft	0°	Auto		start R10 B → A
123234	R10	300ft	0°	Auto		end R10 @ 300ft

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

FLIGHT: B050	DATE: 06/09/2004	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	PAGE: 1 of 1
LOCATION: N Adriatic/Po Valley, N Italy		PROJECT: ADRIEX - flight over Northern Adriatic and along the Po Valley	

GAS CYLINDER PRESSURES	Argon/CO2	N2	CO	HORACE
PRE FLIGHT	2130 psi / 148 bar	1200 psi / 84 bar	620 psi / 44 bar	-- n/a --
POST FLIGHT	psi / bar	psi / bar	psi / bar	-- n/a --
Instrument time check				

TIME (GMT)	HEIGHT (Flight Level)	RUN #	CO SENSITIVITY (Hz/ppbV)	CO BACKGROUND (ppb)	CO BCKGRD.CNT.B (Hz)	CO CONC. (ppb V)	O3 (ppb)	NO (ppb)	NO2 (ppb)	NOx (ppb)	SO2 (ppb)			
05/09/04	FL090	-	88.00	57.23	5036.04	69.67	-	-	-	-	-			
14:21:13	Remarks: Last calibration from previous flight/ground test for comparison with today.													
06/09/04	ground	-	82.03	54.23	4449.03	-	-	-	-	-	-			
04:40:08	Remarks: First cal of day Air sample pipe (ASP) closed. CO cal max values : 531 - 545													
06:23:19	ground	-	81.77	64.09	5240.16	228.595	23	50.03	213.1	263.4	7.80			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 531 – 545													
06:28:00	ground	-	80.68	64.75	5224.41	245.838	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 517 – 523													
06:55:58	ground	78.16	66.99	5236.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 507 – 512													
07:37:21	ground	-	81.00	65.69	5320.65	1093.504	5	494.3	-30.7	463.7	-			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 544 - 553													
07:42:53	ground	-	81.29	65.47	5321.96	764.314	10	494.9	-53.6	441.3	65.1			
	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values : 526 - 529													
08:05:35	FL050	-	82.41	65.27	5378.49	118.268	55	0.11	0.64	0.72	4.23			
	Flow Lamp:	33.88	Press Monocr	0.60	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.41	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.56	PMT °C	26.50
	Remarks: ASP opened. CO cal max values :530 - 537													
08:45:38	FL150	-	83.91	62.87	5275.12	89.545	67	0.10	0.32	0.42	5.00			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 533 – 537 SO2 Low Flow alarm													
09:00:09	FL120	Into R1	84.57	62.04	5246.36	74.138	56	-0.09	0.18	0.09	5.01			
	Flow Lamp:	33.91	Press Monocr	0.57	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.39	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	26.06	PMT °C	25.99
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 526 – 532 R1 started 08:57:42													
09:14:56	FL065	-	86.01	60.88	5236.69	117.680	58	0.01	0.58	0.59	4.02			
	Flow Lamp:	33.88	Press Monocr	0.60	Press Cell:	7.13	Press Cal Gas	2.41	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.83	PMT °C	25.81
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 532 – 535 Pre R2 (CO cal ended just before start of run called)													
09:33:29	FL030	Into R3	87.14	60.58	5279.32	127.187	54	0.06	0.51	0.57	3.80			
	Flow Lamp:	33.99	Press Monocr	0.62	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.43	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.66	PMT °C	25.61
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 529 – 534 R3 started 09:31:06													
10:00:44	FL001	R4	87.60	59.47	5209.26	139.696	55	0.03	1.01	1.04	3.86			
	Flow Lamp:	34.29	Press Monocr	0.62	Press Cell:	7.15	Press Cal Gas	2.43	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.64	PMT °C	25.56
	Remarks: CO cal max values :526 – 530													
10:40:47	FL030	R	87.00	58.80	5115.99	137.112	58	0.06	0.94	1.00	4.15			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 520 - 524													
11:26:35	FI030	Into R8	86.68	58.52	5072.58	153.109	58	0.31	2.36	2.67	4.87			
	Flow Lamp:	33.94	Press Monocr	0.62	Press Cell:	7.14	Press Cal Gas	2.44	Lamp °C	50.00	Monocr °C	25.79	PMT °C	25.72
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 521 – 525 R8 started 11:23:44													
12:25:31	FL030	R10	87.61	56.94	4988.74	120.987	59	0.05	0.91	0.96	3.65			
	Remarks: CO cal max values : 528 - 536													
::	Remarks:													
::	Remarks: ASP closed. CO cal max values :													

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B.050**.....

Date **6.9.04**.....

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU			<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		✓	FFSSP		✓
Satcom C			PCASP		✓
Satcom H		✓	2D-P	X	
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	X	
De-Iced Temp		✓	Cloudscope	X	
Non De-Iced			SID 1		✓
Heimann		✓	SID 2	X	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	X	
G. Eastern			HVPS	X	
J. Williams		✓	<u>Racks:</u>		
Nevzorov	X		INC	X	
TWC	X		CCN / CNC	✓	<i>CNC only</i>
FWVS	X		CVI	✓	✓
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear			PSAP		✓
“ Red	✓	✓	Nephelometer		✓
“ Silicon	✓	X	AMS		✓
“ JO1D	✓	X			
Lower Clear					
“ Red	✓	✓			
“ Silicon	✓	X			
“ JO1D	✓	X			
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	X				
MARSS	X				
DEIMOS	X				
ARIES	X				
SWS / SHIM	✓	✓			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		✓			
ECGC	X				
NOX		✓			
CO		✓	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	X				
PAN		✓			
PERCA	X				
WAS		✓			